

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *CICHORIUM INTYBUS*, LINN. CONSTITUENTS OF THE OIL FROM THE SEEDS.

BY RAM NATH MISRA AND SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT.

Cichorium Intybus Linn., called *Kasni* in Hindustani, belongs to the natural order *Compositae*, and is a native of the north western parts of India. The seeds are reputed to be tonic, demulcent and cooling and they are used in various forms for bilious vomiting and obstructed menstruations. The use of *Kasni* by Indian physicians is much the same as that of *Taraxacum* in Europe (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants," 1918, I, p. 728; Dymock, "Pharmacographica Indica," II, p. 311).

The roots which are used as adulterants for coffee have been chemically examined. Nietzki (*Arch. Pharm.*, 8, 327) separated from the flowers a crystalline glucoside $C_{32}H_{24}O_{19}$, $4\frac{1}{2}H_2O$. The bland oil contained in the seeds is the subject of the present investigation. No crystalline substances could be isolated from the seeds but the seeds have been found to contain the following:—Oil (4.7%), phlobaphenes (1%), tannins (1%) and reducing sugars.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An authentic specimen of *Cichorium Intybus* seeds was procured from the neighbourhood. A sample when burnt left 13.8% of a greyish white ash, consisting of 17.5% water-soluble and 82.5% water-insoluble inorganic material consisting mainly of potassium, sodium (traces), calcium, aluminium, sulphate, phosphate, chloride, carbonate and silica.

Extraction of the Oil.—2.5 Kg. of finely crushed seeds were exhaustively extracted with benzene in a large extraction flask and on removal of the solvent by distillation 118 g. of an oil of the consistency of honey were obtained. It was obtained as a transparent light brown liquid on purification by Fuller's earth and animal charcoal.

Examination of the Oil.—It is a semi-drying oil, free from nitrogen or sulphur and optically inactive. It burns with a partially smoky and non-sooty flame. It has specific gravity 0.9229 at 22°; refractive index, 1.3795 at 30°; solidifying point, -11°; acid value, 11.2; saponification value, 193.1; acetyl value, 14.8; iodine value 95.6; Hehner's value, 93.9 and unsaponifiable matter, 1.7%.

75 G. of the oil were saponified with alcoholic alkali and the soap extracted with ether to remove the unsaponifiable matter. The fatty acids were extracted with petroleum ether after acidifying the soap solution with dilute sulphuric acid. These were semi-solid and had liquifying point 35-38°.; specific gravity, 0·8931 at 40°; neutralisation value, 192·5; mean molecular weight, 291·4 and iodine value, 104·8. 40 G. of these fatty acids were subjected to Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method and separated into saturated and unsaturated portions (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). Table I gives the percentages.

TABLE I.

Acids.	In mixed acids.	In oil.	Iodine value.	Mean M. W.
Saturated ...	21·7%	20·01%	1·6	260·8
Unsaturated ...	78·3	72·19	141·6	280·5

Examination of Unsaturated Acids.—The methods of estimation according to Eibner and Muggenthalor (Lenkowitz, "Chemical Technology of Oils etc.", 5th Ed., Vol. I, p. 573), and Jamiesson and Boughman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1197) failed as no crystalline bromo derivatives were formed. By oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate (Leukowitz, *ibid.*, 1904, Vol. I, p. 360) the presence of oleic and linolic acids alone was proved and these, therefore, may be presumed to constitute the unsaturated portion of the fatty acids for all practical purposes. From the iodine value the percentages of these acids have been calculated and are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Acids.	In unsaturated acids.	In mixed acids.	In oil.
Oleic ...	42·8%	33·5%	30·9%
Linolic ...	57·2	44·8	41·3

Examination of Saturated Acids.—The mixed saturated acids were esterified and the methyl esters fractionally distilled under reduced pressure, the pressure and temperatures being recorded. The weights of the various fractions and their iodine and neutralisation values gave the percentages of stearic and palmitic acids in the mixture. The mean molecular weights of the first and the last fractions were found to lie between 270·3 and 298·4,

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the mean molecular weights of methyl palmitate and stearate respectively. Table III gives the results of distillation and Table IV those of analysis.

TABLE III.

Fraction.	Temperature.	Pressure.	Weight.
I	167-170°	5 mm.	2.58 g.
II	170-172° rose quickly to 183°	"	3.20
III	183-186° rose to 190-200°	"	0.72
Residue	Above 200°.	"	1.42

TABLE IV.

Fraction.	Iodine value.	Sapon. value.	Mean M.W.	Palmitic.	Acids Stearic.	Unsaturated.	
I	1.3	204.6	274.83	2.00 g. 77.52%	0.40 g. 15.51%	0.043 g. 1.66%	
II	1.8	199.3	281.5	1.74	54.56	1.22 38.42	0.074 2.30
III	3.5	192.1	291.8	0.17	24.63	0.48 69.56	0.032 4.48
Residue	13.2	189.7	295.4	0.082	7.08	1.03 88.20	0.240 16.9

Examination of the Unsaponifiable Matter.—This was extracted by ether after saponification of the oil with alcoholic caustic potash. On purification by repeated crystallisation from alcohol it was identified as a phytosterol, m.p. 131-33°.

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